

23 outcomes, and identify gaps for future research. The findings will serve as the evidence base
24 for the subsequent phases of the RemEDy project. The ultimate goal of this research program
25 is to develop a standardized, real-time triage evaluation instrument to enhance triage accuracy,
26 safety, and equity in emergency care.

27 **Keywords:** Emergency medicine; Emergency Nursing; Triage; Mis-triage; Performance
28 evaluation; Triage accuracy

29

30 **Introduction**

31 Emergency department (ED) triage is a fundamental process to ensure that patients receive
32 timely and appropriate care according to the urgency of their condition (1,2). Incorrect
33 assignment of a triage category, also known as mis-triage, may have serious consequences:
34 under-triage may lead to delay of life-saving treatment, while over-triage could result in
35 unnecessary resource use and prolonged waiting times for other patients with time-critical
36 conditions (3–6).

37 Despite the recognized importance of triage and the widespread use of validated triage systems,
38 there is still no clear understanding of how triage performance, including accuracy, reliability
39 and timeliness, are best evaluated (7,8). Studies differ considerably in their definitions of mis-
40 triage, and the outcomes used to measure triage accuracy. Many evaluations are based on
41 retrospective data, simulated scenarios, or chart reviews, which may not adequately represent
42 the complexity and uncertainty of real-time triage in ED (9–11).

43 This heterogeneity and lack of standardization limit the comparability of findings across studies
44 and hinder the development of effective strategies or interventions to improve triage processes
45 (12). To date, no literature review has provided a comprehensive overview of the methods

46 currently used to evaluate triage performance. The development of consistent definitions and
47 validated evaluation methods would improve triage performance evaluations and facilitate
48 benchmarking across healthcare systems worldwide (12). Understanding how triage is
49 currently evaluated and identifying where methodological or conceptual gaps exist, is essential
50 to guide future improvement of patient safety and resource allocation in EDs.

51 The objective of this scoping review is to assess and summarize the existing literature on triage
52 evaluation. Specifically, it aims to define mis-triage, and to identify and analyze existing
53 processes for triage evaluation, including tools, fundamental components, methodologies, and
54 outcomes considered for evaluating triage performance.

55 Review question

- 56 1. What definitions of mis-triage in ED are reported in the literature?
- 57 2. What processes, tools, fundamental components and methodologies are currently used
58 in ED to evaluate triage performance?
- 59 3. What are the indicators and outcomes used to assess triage performance in ED?

60

61 **Methods**

62 The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute
63 (JBI) Manual for Evidence Synthesis (13) and reported according to the Preferred Reporting
64 Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-
65 ScR) (14).

66

67 *Existing or currently ongoing reviews*

68 A preliminary search of MEDLINE, the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews and Joanna
69 Briggs Institute (JBI) Evidence Synthesis was conducted and no existing or currently ongoing
70 systematic or scoping reviews on the topic were identified.

71 *Eligibility criteria*

72 There are numerous question formulation frameworks (15). To further detail the eligibility
73 criteria in the present scoping review, the Participants-Concept-Context (PCC) framework was
74 applied because of its prominent recognition of contextual elements, openness and simplicity
75 (16).

76 *1. Participants*

77 This review will include studies involving clinicians who perform triage, as well as patients
78 undergoing triage in the ED. Studies focusing on patients aged 16 years and older will be
79 included. Studies exclusively addressing specific subgroups of patients (e.g., geriatric,
80 pediatric, disease-specific populations) will be excluded.

81

82 *2. Concept*

83 The main concept of interest is triage performance evaluation. For this review, triage is defined
84 as the process of determining the priority of patients' treatments based on the acuity of their
85 condition (2). Triage performance evaluation refers to the systematic assessment of how
86 accurately this triage process is conducted. This includes the identification and description of
87 tools, fundamental components, and methodologies used to evaluate triage performance. Only
88 studies assessing five-level triage systems will be included. Five-level triage systems were
89 selected as the focus of this review because they are commonly recommended in clinical
90 practice guidelines, reflecting current prevailing standards of emergency care (17).

91

92 4. *Context*

93 This review will consider studies conducted within ED settings. Studies conducted in non-ED
94 environments (e.g., pre-hospital settings, call centers, tele-triage) will be excluded.
95 There are no restrictions based on geographical location or cultural context. However, this
96 review will only include studies conducted in high-income and upper-middle-income
97 countries, according to the World Bank classification, to ensure comparability of healthcare
98 systems, triage processes, and ED organisational structures (18).

99

100 *Types of sources*

101 This scoping review will consider both experimental and quasi-experimental study designs
102 including randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, before and after
103 studies and interrupted time-series studies. In addition, analytical observational studies
104 including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, (nested) case-control studies and cross-
105 sectional studies will be considered for inclusion. This review will also consider descriptive
106 study designs including case series and individual case reports for inclusion.

107 Qualitative studies, including but not limited to, designs such as phenomenology, grounded
108 theory, ethnography, qualitative description and action research will also be considered for
109 inclusion.

110 Only finally published studies will be considered (i.e. no pre-prints). Conference abstracts and
111 editorials will be excluded. Systematic Reviews will be excluded as well, but underlying
112 studies of thematically relevant systematic reviews will be checked and included if relevant.

113 There will be no restrictions regarding language or publication date.

114

115 *Search strategy*

116 A medical information specialist (TF) will systematically search Ovid MEDLIN ALL via Ovid,
117 Embase via Ovid and Scopus using text words and database-specific subject headings. The
118 search strategy will be drafted for Ovid MEDLIN ALL via Ovid and will be translated with the
119 Polyglot Search Translator (19) to the other databases.

120 To further enhance retrieval and strengthen the evidence base, direct backward and forward
121 citation searching will be implemented as supplementary search techniques, following the
122 Terminology, Application, and Reporting of Citation Searching (TARciS) statement (20).

123 *Study/Source of evidence selection*

124 Each title and abstract will be screened by two independent reviewers and assessed against the
125 eligibility criteria of the review. Each full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail,
126 again by two independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion at full text screening stage will be
127 recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the
128 reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion between
129 the two disagreeing reviewers or, ultimately, through discussion with and final verdict by a
130 third reviewer (CHN). The results of the search and the study selection process will be reported
131 in detail in the final scoping review and presented in a PRISMA flow diagram (14).

132 *Data extraction*

133 Data from included studies will be extracted independently by two reviewers using a pre-
134 defined data extraction table developed by the research team. Extracted data will be recorded
135 and managed in a dedicated Microsoft Excel table, which will be used to ensure consistency,
136 transparency, and traceability of extracted information throughout the review process. A

137 corresponding data extraction manual with standardized definitions for the data items will be
138 developed to support the data extractors (*see Appendix I*). The draft data extraction database
139 and manual will first be piloted on 10 papers and will be revised if necessary.
140 MODIFICATIONS will be logged in the data extraction manual. Calibration sessions will be
141 organized where data extraction is jointly discussed to ensure consistency between the data
142 extractors. Any disagreements that arise between the two independent data extractors will be
143 resolved through discussion between them, or, if necessary, through discussion with and final
144 verdict by a third data extractor. If relevant data are missing, unclear, or insufficiently reported,
145 corresponding authors will be contacted by email to request additional information. An initial
146 contact email will be sent, followed by one reminder email after one week if no response is
147 received.

148 *Risk of bias*

149 A formal risk of bias assessment will not be conducted, as it is not applicable to the objectives
150 of this scoping review.

151 *Data analysis and presentation*

152 Extracted data will be analyzed using a descriptive analytical framework guided by the
153 predefined data extraction table. Quantitative data will be summarized using frequencies and
154 descriptive statistics, while qualitative data will be analyzed thematically to explore how triage
155 performance is defined, evaluated, and measured across studies. The analysis will map
156 evaluation methods, reference standards, outcome domains, and key indicators, highlighting
157 patterns, inconsistencies, and gaps in the literature.

158 Results will be presented through narrative synthesis and summary tables, supported by visual
159 mapping where appropriate, to illustrate the scope and variability of triage evaluation

160 approaches. Importantly, the findings of this scoping review will be used to inform the
161 development of an evidence-based pool of candidate items for a prototype triage evaluation
162 instrument, to be developed and refined in subsequent phases of the RemEDy project.

163

164 **Conclusion**

165 This scoping review will systematically map triage performance evaluation in EDs. The
166 findings of this scoping review will provide the evidence base for the initial development of a
167 standardized, real-time triage evaluation instrument within the RemEDy project. By clarifying
168 definitions of mis-triage and mapping existing triage evaluation processes, components, and
169 outcomes, the review will inform the selection of possible items for the envisioned real-time
170 triage evaluation instrument. These findings will directly feed into the subsequent phases of
171 the RemEDy project, including a modified Delphi study, aimed at refining, validating, and
172 operationalising the triage evaluation instrument (21). Together, these steps will support the
173 development of a robust, evidence-based instrument designed to improve triage accuracy,
174 safety, and equity in emergency care.

175 **Funding**

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178 **Conflicts of interest**

179 There is no conflict of interest in this project.

180

181 **References**

182

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249 **Appendix I: Data extraction instrument**

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251 Domain 1: study characteristics

Field	Description/Data to extract
Author	Last name of first author
Year	Year of publication
Title	Title of the article
Journal	Name of the journal
DOI	DOI link or another identifier
Country	Country where the study was conducted
ED setting	<p>Use one or more of the following labels:</p> <p>Level of care</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary ED: small, local ED with basic emergency services, often rural • Secondary ED: regional hospital with moderate capacity and specialist access • Tertiary ED: large hospital with advanced services • Other [add explanation] <p>Institutional label</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic ED: affiliated with an academic medical center, conducts research • Teaching ED. Focuses on clinical training for resident and students. • Community ED: any ED not primary and exclusively involved in research

Field	Description/Data to extract
	Other [add explanation]
ED visits/year	Report the number of admissions per year (if applicable)
Type of study	<p>Use one of the following labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-center • Multi-center <p>Design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Randomized control trial: An experimental study in which participants are randomly assigned to intervention or control groups to test causal effects. • Explanatory mixed-method: A mixed-method design where quantitative data are collected first and qualitative data are used to explain quantitative findings. • Exploratory mixed-method: A mixed-method design starting with qualitative data to explore a phenomenon, followed by quantitative data to test or expand findings. • Conversion parallel mixed-method: Quantitative and qualitative data are collected simultaneously and integrated during interpretation to provide a comprehensive understanding.

Field	Description/Data to extract
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cohort study: An observational study following a group over time to assess relationships between exposures and outcomes. • Quasi-experimental study: An intervention study without random assignment, used when randomization is not feasible or ethical. • Descriptive study: A study that describes characteristics or distributions of a population or phenomenon without examining causal relationships. • Other [add explanation] <p>Temporal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prospective • Retrospective • Pre-post • Cross-sectional • Other [add explanation]
Aims	<p>Aim(s) or research question(s) of the study</p> <p>Copy-paste the aims reported by the author (starting with the word “to + [verb]”)</p>

252

253

254 Domain 2: Mis-triage (research question 1)

Field	Description/Data to extract
Mis-triage definition	<p>How mis-triage is defined.</p> <p>Copy-paste the definition that the authors in the article use (if applicable)</p>
Under-triage definition	<p>How under-triage is defined.</p> <p>Copy-paste the definition that the authors in the article use (if applicable)</p>
Over-triage definition	<p>How over-triage is defined.</p> <p>Copy-paste the definition that the authors in the article use (if applicable)</p>

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263 Domain 3: Triage evaluation processes (research question 2)

Field	Description/Data to extract
Triage clinicians	<p>Individuals whose triage performance is being evaluated in the study.</p> <p>Use one or more of the following labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nurses • Physicians • Paramedics • Students • Other [add explanation]
Number of triage clinicians	<p>Report the total number of clinicians whose triage performance was assessed in the study.</p>
Triage evaluators	<p>Individuals who conduct the evaluation of the triage clinicians</p> <p>Use one or more of the following labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triage nurse experts • Physician experts • Researchers • Expert panel • Other [add explanation]

Expert panel composition	If the option <i>Expert Panel</i> is selected in the “Triage Evaluators” column, please complete this column with information regarding the composition of the expert panel.
Number of cases	Number of cases assessed/participants (if applicable)
Sampled population	Describe the population used for triage evaluation (real patients or cases or other).
Total sample cases	Report the total number of triage cases/patients assessed or included in the evaluation.
Triage system	<p>Type of validated triage system in use</p> <p>Use one or more of the following labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency severity index (ESI) • Manchester Triage System (MTS) • Canadian triage and acuity scale (CTAS) • Australasian triage scale (ATS) • Other [add abbreviation] <p>Reminder: if a new system is added, report abbreviation and in bracket extended version → Example: TTS (Tuscany Triage System)</p>

<p>Evaluation Methods</p>	<p>Specify the methodology with one of these labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • chart reviews • scenario • audit • clinical vignettes • standardized surveys • mixed-methods approaches [add explanation] • automated electronic medical record analysis • simultaneous triage (instrument) • simultaneous triage (evaluators) • comparison with gold standard • Other [add explanation]
<p>Methodology description</p>	<p>Report (copy-paste) how the methodology was applied during the study.</p>
<p>Fundamental Components Assessed</p>	<p>Indicate whether each of the following <i>fundamental components of triage evaluation</i> was assessed in the study. For each category, assign:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 = assessed • 0 = not assessed <p>Triage process outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accuracy

- Reliability
- Validity
- Efficiency (time to triage/resource utilization)

Clinical outcomes

- Mortality
- Admission
- ICU admission
- Adverse event
- Acute emergency treatment or unanticipated life-saving intervention

Operational outcomes

- Length of stay
- Wait times (time to first physician contact)
- Boarding time
- Left without being seen
- Overcrowding measure

Patient-related outcomes

- Satisfaction
- Others (e.g. fear, comfort)

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Field	Description/Data to extract
<p>Triage process outcomes</p> <p>Accuracy</p>	<p>This section describes the main outcomes used to assess accuracy.</p> <p>Report the percentage of mis-triage and/or correct triage as indicated by the study authors.</p> <p>If both are reported, extract both values separately.</p> <p>Specify whether the percentage refers to overall mis-triage, under-triage, or over-triage.</p>
<p>Triage process outcomes</p> <p>Reliability</p>	<p>Indicate whether the study assessed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - inter-rater (agreement between different raters) - or intra-rater (consistency of the same rater over time) <p>reliability of triage performance.</p> <p>For inter-rater reliability, specify between whom was it assessed.</p> <p>Extract the statistical measure(s) reported to quantify reliability. Use the drop-down menu below to specify the measure type.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cohen’s kappa (κ) - Weighted kappa - Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) - Percent agreement (%) - Fleiss’ kappa - Krippendorff’s alpha - Correlation coefficient (Pearson’s r / Spearman’s ρ)

Field	Description/Data to extract
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not specified / qualitative agreement
<p>Triage process outcomes</p> <p><u>Validity</u></p>	<p>Indicate whether the study assessed any form of validity of the triage system.</p> <p>Specify the <i>type of validity</i> evaluated (construct, criterion, or predictive) and extract the statistical measure(s) or method(s) used.</p> <p>Use the drop-down menus provided for each validity type.</p> <p>Construct validity</p> <p>Evaluates whether triage levels reflect actual differences in patient severity (known-groups approach).</p> <p>Examples include comparing triage levels with hospital admission, ICU admission, or mortality.</p> <p><u>Drop-down menu options:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chi-square across categories - ANOVA / Kruskal–Wallis - Spearman rank correlation - Ordinal logistic regression (Outcome ~ Triage level as ordered factor) - Relative risk / odds ratio by level (reported as gradient) <p>Criterion validity</p>

Field	Description/Data to extract
	<p>Assesses the agreement between triage decisions and an external reference standard (“gold standard”) such as expert judgment or a validated triage scale.</p> <p><u>Drop-down menu options:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert panel - Validated scale (ESI/MTS/CTAS/ATS) - Guideline-based reference <p>Predictive validity</p> <p>Examines how well triage categories predict future clinical outcomes (e.g., mortality, hospital admission, ICU transfer).</p> <p>Drop-down menu options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AUROC / AUC - C-statistic - Logistic regression (OR or AOR) - Cox proportional hazard (HR)
Clinical outcome	<p>Specify the clinical outcome:</p> <p><u>Mortality</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mortality in ED • Mortality within 24 hours • Mortality at 48 hours • Mortality at 72 hours

Field	Description/Data to extract
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mortality at 7 days • Mortality at 30 days • Mortality at 1 year • Mortality [add the timepoint] • Hospital admission normal ward • Hospital admission ICU <p>Adverse event or acute emergency treatment or unanticipated life-saving intervention [please report the one listed in the article]</p>
Operational outcomes	<p>Specify the operation outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of stay • Wait times • Boarding • Left without being seen • Overcrowding measure • Other [add explanation]
Patients reported outcome	<p>Specify the patient centered-outcome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients' satisfaction • Other [add explanation]